

was slightly modified and then used to prepare the title compounds. A solution of sodium metal (0.25 g, 0.0012 mol) in propargyl alcohol (50 ml) was added to a stirred solution of appropriate benzyl bromide (0.01 ml) in propargyl alcohol (50 ml) at 60°. The reaction mixture was then heated on a water-bath at 60–80° for about 4 h, then cooled to room temperature and neutralised with 5% hydrochloric acid and filtered. The propargyl alcohol in the filtrate was removed on a rotary evaporator. The residue left was treated with water and the oily layer was extracted into ether. The ether layer was separated, washed with water, dried and concentrated under reduced pressure. The crude residue was distilled fractionally at reduced pressure. The data are given in Table 1.

Evaluation of synergistic activity by Topical Application method⁶: Synergistic activity of the benzyl 2-propynyl ethers (3a–r) was determined with mobam and supracide insecticides against resistant female house flies of the Rutgers A-strain. The required number of house flies were chilled or anaesthetised with carbon dioxide and a solution of the test compound and insecticide (1 : 5) was prepared in appropriate concentrations. One microliter of the solutions containing the appropriate dose was applied to the dorsal region of the flies with the help of an automatic syringe dispenser. The flies were then held in plastic petridishes and cotton soaked in milk was provided. Tests were performed in triplicate using ten flies per test. The percent mortality after 24 h of the three sets of flies was averaged.

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Synthesis of some 2-(2'-Methoxybenzoyl)-coumaran-3-ones

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IN continuation of our investigation¹ on coumaran-3-ones, we report here the synthesis of some 2-(2'-methoxybenzoyl)coumaran-3-ones. These coumaran-3-ones have been obtained by two routes. In the first route (Scheme 1) the 2-hydroxyacetophenones (1a–e) were condensed at low temperature (0–5°) with *o*-methoxybenzoic acid in pyridine with phosphorus oxychloride as a condensing agent, to give the corresponding benzoyloxyacetophenones (2a–e) in 70–90% yield. These esters on bromination with copper(II) bromide in dry dioxan afforded the ω -bromoacetophenones (3a–e) which on refluxing with KOH in dioxan gave the desired coumaran-3-ones, obviously through the unstable products (4)². Yield at all stages were excellent.

Scheme 1

Scheme 2 was designed not only to give a second route but *inter alia* afford a verification of the contention of Wadodkar and Daifode³, that the 3-bromochromones undergo ring contraction on refluxing with KOH, and produce the related

coumaran-3-ones. For the purpose, the esters (2a-e) were subjected to Baker-Venkataraman rearrangement to yield the respective 1,3-diketones. The crude diketones were then cyclised by refluxing their acetic acid solution with trace amount of hydrochloric acid to yield the corresponding chromones (7a-e) in moderate yield. The chromones were then brominated with copper(II) bromide in ethyl acetate-chloroform mixture (2:1) to give the 3-bromochromones (8a-e). Bromination of chromones has been established to yield the 3-bromochromones in other cases also⁴. In fact, the conversion of the bromochromones to the coumaran-3-ones (which are bromine free) can occur only if the bromine is at position-3 of the chromon ring. The 3-H proton of a chromone shows pmr signal at δ 6.3-6.7. The bromochromones (8a, d), for example, do not show any signal in the region δ 6-7, clearly indicating the absence of the proton at position-3. The bromochromones on refluxing with ethanolic potassium hydroxide gave the desired coumaranones (5a-e). The compounds obtained by this route were identical with the coumaran-3-ones obtained by Scheme 1.

Scheme 2

Experimental

All m.ps. are uncorrected. The infrared spectra were recorded on a Backman IR-20 spectrophotometer and the pmr in a EM-360 spectrometer.

Nuclear brominated hydroxyacetophenones were obtained by the reported method⁶.

Benzoyloxyacetophenone (2a-e): A mixture of **1** (0.065 mol) and *o*-methoxybenzoic acid (0.007 mol) in dry pyridine (10 ml) was treated with phosphorous oxychloride (0.3 ml) in drops with stirring (2 h) below 5°. It was left overnight in an ice-chest and then poured into ice-HCl mixture. The resulting solid was triturated with sodium hydroxide solution (2%), washed with water and recrystallised from suitable solvent. The m.p., yield and solvent of crystallisation were as follows: **2a** (84%), m.p. 84-85° (EtOH); **2b** (70%), m.p. 91° (MeOH); **2c** (88%), m.p. 71-72° (MeOH); **2d** (63%), m.p. 48-49° (MeOH); **2e** (90%), m.p. 108-09° (MeOH).

ω -Bromobenzoyloxyacetophenone (3a-e): Anhydrous CuBr₂ (0.01 mol) in dry dioxan (20 ml) was refluxed for 0.5 h with exclusion of moisture. An ester (2a-e; 0.005 mol) was then added to it and refluxing was continued until a gray-white precipitate was obtained (4-5 h). The dioxan filtrate was concentrated and diluted with ice-water. The solid which separated was washed and crystallised from proper solvent. The yield, m.p. and solvent of crystallisation are as follows: **3a** (83%), m.p. 100° (AcOH); **3b** (80%), m.p. 96° (EtOH); **3c** (73%), m.p. 65° (EtOH); **3d** (65%), m.p. 52° (EtOH); **3e** (90%), m.p. 105° (MeOH).

Coumaran-3-ones (5a-e) (Scheme 1): A mixture of the ω -bromo-ester (0.005 mol) in dry dioxan (15 ml) and powdered KOH (0.015 mol) was refluxed for 1 h and then cooled and poured into ice/dilute H₂SO₄. The resulting solid which was washed and recrystallised: 7-bromo-5-chloro-2-(2'-methoxybenzoyl)coumaran-3-one (**5a**; 75%), m.p. 90° (AcOH); ν_{\max} (KBr) 2960 and 1645 cm⁻¹; δ (CDCl₃; 60 MHz) 2.7 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.7 (1H, s, OH and proton), 7.2-7.6 (6H, m, ArH); 7-bromo-5-methyl-2-(2'-methoxybenzoyl)coumaran-3-one (**5b**; 90%), m.p. 89° (EtOH); ν_{\max} (KBr) 2950, 1665 and 870 cm⁻¹; 5-bromo-7-methyl-2-(2'-methoxybenzoyl)coumaran-3-one (**5c**; 73%), m.p. 74-75° (EtOH); 5-methyl-2-(2'-methoxybenzoyl)coumaran-3-ones (**5d**; 80%), m.p. 65° (MeOH); δ (CDCl₃; 90 MHz) 2.4 (3H, s, CH₃), 2.82 (3H, s, OCH₃), 7.2 (1H, s, OH) and 6.6-8.2 (7H, m, ArH); 7,5-dibromo-2-(2'-methoxybenzoyl)coumaran-3-one (**5e**; 87%), m.p. 107-08° (EtOH).

Chromones (7a-e): A mixture of 2a-e (0.01 mol) and powdered KOH (0.03 mol) in dry pyridine (10 ml) was stirred at 60-70° till the mixture turned to a thick yellow paste and left at room temperature for 3 h. It was then poured into crushed ice containing HCl and the resulting crude product was dried and refluxed with acetic acid and traces of HCl. On working up colourless crystals of chromones were obtained which were recrystallised from ethanol: **5a** (90%), m.p. 108°; δ (CDCl₃; 90 MHz) 3.2 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.8 (1H, s, C-3) and 7.2-8.6 (6H, m, ArH); **5b** (92%), m.p. 57°; **5c** (80%), m.p. 77-78°; **5d** (72%), m.p. 58°; **5e** (95%), m.p. 116-17°.

3-Bromoflavone (8a-e); To a solution of cupric bromide (1g) in ethyl acetate-chloroform mixture (2:1), chromone (0.3 mol) was added and the solution was refluxed until gray-white precipitate of cuprous bromide was obtained (6-12 h). It was then filtered and the filtrate was evaporated to dryness. The resulting solid was crystallised from proper solvent. The yield, m.p. and solvent of crystallisation were as follows: **8a** (80%), m.p. 103°; δ (CDCl₃; 90 MHz) 3.2 (3H, s, OCH₃) and 7.2-8.6 (6H, m, ArH); **8b** (75%), m.p. 93° (EtOH); **8c** (82%), m.p. 71-72° (MeOH); **8d** (70%), m.p. 59° (EtOH); **8e** (90%), m.p. 112°.

Coumaran-3-ones (5a-e) (Scheme 2): A mixture of the 3-bromochromone (0.01 mol) dissolved in ethanol (30 ml) and ethanolic KOH (70 ml; 25%) was gently refluxed for 2 h. The solution was then poured into ice/HCl (2N). The resulting solid was washed and recrystallised: **5a** (70%), **5b** (85%), **5c** (65%), **5d** (75%) and **5e** (85%).

The products showed no depression on admixture (1:1) with coumaran-3-ones obtained by the other route (Scheme 1).

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Studies on Flavonoids. Part-II. Synthesis and Antimicrobial Activity of 8-Bromo-7-n-butoxy-6-nitro-flavones, -flavonols and -flavanones

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CONSIDERING the therapeutic and synthetic importance of flavonoids¹, it was thought worthwhile to synthesise some new flavonoids and evaluate their antimicrobial activity.

The present work reports the synthesis of 8-bromo-7-n-butoxy-6-nitro-flavones (2), -flavonols (3) and -flavanones (4). These are derived from previously synthesised² 2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4'-n-butoxy-5'-nitrochalcones (1) which have been prepared from 2-hydroxy-3-bromo-4-n-butoxy-5-nitroacetophenone and various aromatic aldehydes and tested for their antimicrobial activity².

The chalcones (1) on oxidation with selenium dioxide in n-amyl alcohol³ were smoothly converted into the flavones (2). The chalcones (1) when subjected to Alger-Flynn-Oyamada oxidation⁴ using alkaline hydrogen peroxide gave the flavonols (3). Cyclisation⁵ of the chalcones (1) in ethanol in presence of sulphuric acid (10%) yielded the corresponding flavanones (4) (Scheme 1). The structures of the compounds have been confirmed by elemental analysis, ir and pmr spectra. The compounds have been screened for their antimicrobial activity.

Scheme 1

Antimicrobial activity: The compounds were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities at a concentration of 50 μg by cup-plate method⁶ against gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, gram-negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* and fungus *Aspergillus niger*, and were compared with chloramphenicol, penicillin G and streptomycin. The compounds showed strong activity (15-25 mm, zone of inhibition) against *S. aureus*, and medium or weak activity (6-15 mm) against *E. coli*. Most of the compounds were found strongly active (15-30 mm) against *A. niger*. It is concluded that some of the compounds containing chlorine atom/atoms introduced in aryl part of the flavonoid molecule were found to be most active, while the others possess moderate or weak activity against both bacteria and fungi.